

How do problematisations “materialise”? A neopragmatic perspective on the (in-)visibilisation of justice concerns in AIED

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ABSTRACT

The Foucault-inspired notion of problematisation suggests that AIED is powerfully shaped by public discourse. But how do such societal discourses actually *materialise* in digital learning tools? This article introduces the Sociology of Critique – a strand of French Pragmatic Sociology – as a framework for clarifying such processes. We examine how public problematisations of school education are reconfigured during the business-driven development of EdTech. Using examples from our research on the Swiss EdTech startup field, we reveal how questions of social justice become (in-)visibilised in these interplays, reframing equity as a scaling problem rather than engaging with complex educational realities and contested meanings of equity and justice. Central to our analysis is the concept of ‘short-circuiting’ which sensitises us to how seemingly self-evident assumptions allow bypassing crucial justice-related considerations in development contexts. We conclude by discussing how sociology can leverage its position to enable critical engagement.

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Introduction

The emergence of AIED¹ (AI-based educational technologies) raises both hopes and fears regarding social justice. On the one hand, AI is presented as a tool for overcoming educational inequalities by radically personalising learning on a mass basis (Dumont and Ready 2023; Regan and Jesse 2019). On the other hand, there is an increasing acknowledgement of risks such as algorithmic bias and discrimination (Baker and Hawn 2022; Eynon 2024; Gillani et al. 2023; Selwyn et al. 2020). Although questions of social justice thus form an important element of current AIED debates, we have a very limited understanding of how justice concerns are taken into account in concrete practices of developing or deploying digital learning tools. As we argue in this article, intricate dynamics of visibilising and invisibilising such concerns take place when shifting from the level of grand discourse to everyday situations ‘on the ground’.

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The Foucault-inspired notion of problematisation (Bacchi 2009, 2012) offers a valuable starting point for unravelling such dynamics of visibilising and invisibilising justice concerns. It centres our attention on how these issues are framed as a ‘problem to tackle’ in AIED discourses, and on the kind of solutions that are considered feasible and appropriate. Following this understanding, Rahm and Rahm-Skåjeby (2023) suggest to think of AIED tools as ‘materialised problematisations’ in order to capture their embedding in powerful discursive orders.

This article builds on this idea and explores approaches to a fuller understanding of how problematisations actually ‘materialise.’ Existing frameworks struggle to explain how problem understandings transform as they move from rhetoric to practice. Understanding this transformation requires a theoretical approach that bridges problematisations and everyday problem-solving activities. In this article, we present the Sociology of Critique – an important strand of French Pragmatic Sociology (FPS) – as theoretical foundation for thinking about such processes in novel ways. In contrast to other strands of pragmatic sociology that maintain a ‘flat ontology’ (most prominently Actor-Network-Theory), the Sociology of Critique emphasises the role of pre-existing moral grammars that inform how actors navigate uncertain situations, making it especially valuable for examining how justice concerns transform as they move between different fields of practice.

Our article follows two interwoven objectives. First, we outline the guiding tenets of FPS, focusing on the Sociology of Critique as one of its main variants. Second, we demonstrate its analytical value for researching and deliberating problematisation dynamics as they evolve around justice issues in AIED. We begin our discussion in section 2 with a brief presentation of the research context that motivates this paper and from which its empirical illustrations are taken. Section 3 turns to the notion of ‘problematisation,’ arguing that important findings from critical EdTech studies can be related to each other through this heuristic lens. However, significant conceptual challenges remain for such a problem-centred perspective, including how to bridge dominant discourses and the problem understandings that guide everyday practices. Section 4 discusses the Sociology of Critique as a possible starting point for addressing these challenges. In sections 5 to 7, we illustrate how pragmatic sociology advances our understanding of the dynamics through which social justice issues become visible or invisible in AIED contexts, and how it helps define tasks and roles for critical social research in relation to these dynamics.

Our primary contribution is conceptual: we refine the notion of problematisation by showing how the Sociology of Critique advances our understanding of the translation between public narratives and situational problem-solving activities. This conceptual refinement is particularly important in the AIED context, since contemporary EdTech developments involve profound rearrangements of educational orders and novel interactions between actor groups (including private businesses and new regulatory bodies). Drawing on examples from the Swiss EdTech startup field, we point to concrete mechanisms that result from these rearrangements – most notably the potentially harmful ‘short-circuiting’ that happens when seemingly self-evident assumptions allow bypassing crucial considerations in situations of designing and developing AIED. While our empirical observations are of course context-specific, they demonstrate the kind of dynamics that a FPS-enriched problematisation lens can uncover, suggesting directions for further research on how EdTech development reconfigures educational justice concerns.

Guiding objective and research context

This article is intended as a theoretical position paper that explores the potential of the pragmatic Sociology of Critique to advance problem-centred heuristics and frameworks for sociological analysis. More specifically, we argue for a problematisation perspective that foregrounds the tensions and ruptures that emerge within arenas of public and political discourse, as well as between these discourses and the immediate contexts of EdTech development.

This undertaking is motivated by an ongoing research project on the interplay of the pedagogical and the technological field in the development of EdTech in Switzerland, funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation. Observations in this project lead us to suspect concerning patterns regarding social justice issues in practices of developing and using such technologies, patterns that seem to emerge from how notions and assumptions developed in one field (politics, pedagogy, technology) are received and made use of in other fields. We refer to this research context throughout this article to corroborate the case for an enhanced problematisation lens and to provide selected empirical examples for illustrative purposes.

The empirical examples presented in sections 5 to 7 should accordingly be understood as exploratory insights, not as comprehensive or definitive findings. These examples are taken from two project parts. First, we present key findings from the pilot study that preceded our currently ongoing project; this pilot study investigated current EdTech discourses on the basis of an extensive collection of online documents. Details on this study and findings from it have been published elsewhere (Horvath, Frei, and Steinberg 2023; Frei, Steinberg, and Horvath 2024). Second, we include a number of examples from our project part on the Swiss EdTech field which comprises two components: (1) We conducted 12 in-depth interviews with EdTech startups exploring the challenges they encounter while developing products and establishing their enterprises. (2) We conducted ethnographic research at EdTech events to map and understand the ‘EdTech ecosystem’ that shapes how startups conceptualise and develop their companies and products.

Drawing on these components of our project, we aim to demonstrate how a sophisticated problematisation lens can sensitize us to crucial justice-related dynamics in the EdTech field. Our multi-field perspective underpins our theoretical argument about how problematisations transform as they move across different domains of practice, suggesting valuable directions for further research on educational technology and social justice. The following section turns to the reasoning behind this argument, starting from the notion of problematisation that leads us to ask how exactly we might think of political narratives as ‘materialising’ in AIED.

Problematisation as guiding heuristic for critical EdTech studies

EdTech solutionism and the case for a problematisation lens

Critical scholars have repeatedly identified solutionist narratives as a crucial feature of the global EdTech industry (Morozov 2014; Nachtwey and Seidl 2020). Selwyn (2011, 57) prominently spoke of EdTech as ‘solution in search of a problem.’ This solutionism should not be dismissed as harmless or naive belief in the capacity of technology to bring easy answers to complex problems. Rather, it is an integral part of a transformation entailing troubling

shifts of power and control over public education (see e.g. Davies et al. 2022; Komljenovic et al. 2023; Williamson 2018, 2022).

Given the key role of solutionist narratives for the EdTech field and acknowledging that any solutionist rhetoric is the flip-side of a specific (even if implicit) problem definition, Rahm (2023; see also: Rahm and Rahm-Skågeby 2023) suggests problematisation as a guiding heuristic for critical EdTech studies. This suggestion builds on the late Foucault's identification of problematisation as overarching conceptual framework of hiHorvath et al. 2023s work (Foucault 1991; Lawlor and Nale 2014). The concept of problematisation emphasizes that the definition of problems is an active process, that actors always could have problematised the same situation differently (Bacchi 2012). It hence runs counter to any deterministic or representational account of social problems. For Foucault, problematisation is both a privileged phenomenon to investigate and a methodology, a strategy of enquiry ('problematising problematisations'). Conceptually, problematisation allows us to focus on logics and practices of construal – on how social issues are constituted as problems in and through discourse – while avoiding the pitfalls of radical constructivism. In any problematic situation, there is some 'real' difficulty or uncertainty to start with, but only through problematisation does this difficulty become tangible, negotiable, and manageable. Every form of problematisation comes with an accompanying space of solutions which are considered appropriate, feasible, acceptable, and realistic for dealing with the problem at hand. How a phenomenon is framed as a problem therefore not only mirrors cultural values and power relations, but is also highly consequential (Bacchi 2009).

To give an example, consider how the narrative of personalised learning in AIED problematises traditional classroom education (Buckingham Shum and Luckin 2019; Dishon 2017). When AIED companies frame traditional teaching as unable to cater to individual learning speeds and styles, they simultaneously construct a specific problem (the 'one-size-fits-all' approach). This problematisation foregrounds certain aspects of education (individual learning pace, measurable outcomes) while backgrounding others (social learning, teacher-student relationships) (Ben-Porath and Ben Shahar 2017). At the same time, it positions AI-driven solutions as a natural answer to the problem as it is framed (Dishon 2021; Selwyn 2011).

Problematisations as interface and the puzzle of their materialisation

The heuristic power of problematisation for critical EdTech studies lies in its interface character. Problematisations are inherently interwoven with other key elements of the digital transformation of education, such as the rise and role of new actors in the educational field (Cherner and Mitchell 2021; Davies et al. 2022; Macgilchrist 2019; Williamson 2022), changing forms of educational governance (Komljenovic et al. 2023; Williamson 2015, 2016), educational values and moral orders (Gray and Boling, 2016; Ben-Porath and Ben Shahar 2017), pedagogical presuppositions (Bartolomé, Castañeda, and Adell 2018; Buckingham Shum and Luckin 2019; Dishon 2017, 2021), or visions of possible and desirable educational futures (Facer and Selwyn 2021; Linderoth, Hultén, and Stenliden 2024; Rahm 2023; Smith and Fressoli, 2021; Williamson 2022).

Mirroring this interlocking of problematisations with power, actors, values, pedagogies, and educational imaginaries, Rahm and Rahm-Skågeby (2023, 1147) argue that EdTech

‘can be fruitfully analysed as “policies frozen in silicon” – or as ‘materialised problematisations.’ This is an intriguing and important conjecture. But how exactly can we conceive of such processes that translate problematisations into concrete digital learning tools and environments? After all, problematisations are first and foremost framings on the level of public and political discourse. Problematisations define governmental strategies. These strategies enable and restrict practices of designing, developing, and deploying EdTech – but how exactly do they inform and structure mundane practices ‘on the ground’? How exactly do they develop material effects?

Focusing solely on the level of public discourse risks obscuring the complex processes through which problematisations are translated, negotiated, and potentially transformed as they inform the development of specific tools and environments. Accounting for these dynamics requires a theoretical framework that can bridge the gap between discourse and practice and illuminate the challenges and tensions that arise in the materialisation of EdTech problematisations. Our analytical objective in this article is to grasp specific dynamics and mechanisms that shape these transformations. These include processes where connections presented as self-evident in public narratives allow certain considerations to be bypassed in practical development contexts (we will refer to such specific dynamics as *short-circuiting* later in this text). We argue that identifying such mechanisms provides valuable analytical tools for exploring how justice concerns are reconfigured in educational technology development cycles.

In the following, we introduce French Pragmatic Sociology (FPS) as a theoretical foundation for investigating such dynamics. Section 4 introduces FPS with a focus on its links to problem-centred research heuristics. Sections 5 to 7 then discuss how this perspective advances our understanding of problematisation dynamics in the current EdTech and AIED landscape, moving from the plural moral orders that inform public narratives and concrete ‘school world’ arrangements to the problems that EdTech developers face in their everyday work. Our empirical examples focus on EdTech startups (as opposed to corporate EdTech) as crucial development contexts and on the conspicuous dynamics of visibilisation and invisibilisation of social justice concerns that emerge in these contexts. We conclude by asking how to (re-)problematisate problematisation dynamics as the ones described, leading us to discuss the roles and responsibilities that the presented analytical perspective implies for critical sociologists.

French Pragmatic Sociology: from problematisation to problem-solving practices

French Pragmatic Sociology looks back on four decades of development (Barthe et al. 2014; Diaz Bone and de Larquier 2020; Holmqvist 2022; Holmqvist and Telling 2024; Horvath, Frei, and Steinberg 2023). This development has been marked by a nuanced differentiation from Bourdieu’s critical sociology (Bénatouïl 1999). Its main departure from a Bourdieusian framework lies in its conception of social actors. French Pragmatic Sociology emphasises that we need to conceive of social actors as competent, focusing on the critical capacities that allow them to coordinate and communicate in uncertain situations and demanding social worlds (Boltanski and Thévenot 1983, 1999). With this move towards actors handling problematic situations, FPS offers valuable resources for addressing the limitations of

problematism as a purely discursive concept. Where Foucault-inspired approaches excel at identifying how issues are constituted as problems in public discourse, FPS provides tools for understanding how these problematisations are translated, transformed, and sometimes distorted in everyday situations of uncertainty.

The pragmatic conception of social actors goes hand in hand with a specific epistemological standpoint. Any imagination of social research as being in a privileged epistemic position is rejected. There is also no neutral outsider perspective that would allow transcendent judgements of truth or justice. Rather, social researchers need to acknowledge their 'complex interiority' (Boltanski 2011, 26), the immersive position-within from which they construe their research interests and – willingly or not – are always involved in the social worlds they investigate (Boltanski, Honneth, and Celikates 2014). The main task for critical sociologists is accordingly no longer seen in 'denouncing', 'debunking', or 'unveiling', but rather in 'assembling' and 'enabling.' This means broadening and deepening the possibilities of critical engagement for as many actors as possible (Boltanski 2011; Latour 2004). Applied to the field of EdTech, this epistemological stance provides innovative perspectives on questions of justice, but, of course, comes with its own specific challenges. Most importantly, it raises the question of how to balance the tasks of inquiry and critique (Horvath, Frei, and Steinberg 2023), and how to actively and justifiably position oneself in relation to developments unfolding between the business world, education politics, and pedagogical practice.

The epistemological-cum-political perspective characteristic for FPS closely mirrors traditional pragmatic thinking. Also very much in line with this pragmatic heritage, *problems* stand at the centre of FPS. This problem-orientation defines FPS's methodological outlook which focuses on uncertain situations – situations of conflict, dispute, or crisis which social actors need to resolve (Barthe et al. 2014). This pragmatic focus on problems provides a crucial bridge between Foucauldian problematisation and everyday problem-solving practices. While problematisation helps us understand how education gets framed as problematic on the level of public and political discourse, FPS draws our attention to how actors perceive, define, navigate, and resolve concrete problems in practice. This dual perspective is essential for understanding the relationship between grand narratives about educational transformation and the actual development and deployment of AIED solutions.

Notwithstanding their shared orientations, there are important differences between different strands of French Pragmatic Sociology (Guggenheim and Potthast 2012; Latour 2009). This article builds on the Sociology of Critique (Boltanski 2011; Boltanski, Honneth, and Celikates 2014) which has emerged as an important counterpart to Actor-Network Theory (ANT) within the broader FPS movement. ANT can be considered the currently most prominent variant of FPS in the international social research landscape (Callon and Latour 1981; Fenwick and Edwards 2010; Latour 1996; Law 1992). While both strands share a focus on actors' competencies and a rejection of any assumption of a privileged epistemic position for social scientists, they differ in their understanding of social order. Latour's flat ontology precludes assuming any pre-existing order, thereby also restricting the role of social research to providing dense accounts with descriptive complexity (Couldry 2020). In contrast, the Sociology of Critique emphasises the relevance of established moral, political, and epistemic orders for understanding how social actors define and handle uncertain situations (Boltanski and Thévenot 2006).

The role and relevance of such orders is the first cornerstone for the specific problematisation lens we outline in the following. Taking pre-existing orders into account allows us to refine our understanding of problematisations in two important regards: first, by shifting attention to the tension-ridden moral grammars that inform problem definitions, second by sensitizing us to the ruptures that can emerge in real-world arrangements (such as everyday classroom situations). The following section will discuss how such plural orders manifest in public narratives surrounding AIED. This will be an important prerequisite for the next step in understanding how such grand problematisations become effective (or not) in situational problem-solving agency 'on the ground' (section 6), and also an important anchor-point for defining roles and tasks for critical sociologists (section 7).

Plural orders in AIED narratives: tension-ridden moral grammars

It is a central tenet of French Pragmatic Sociology and the Sociology of Critique that actors can draw on a *plurality* of moral orders to coordinate in uncertain situations (Putnam 2002; Thévenot 2007). This is actually a double tenet: it captures, first, the idea of moral grammars that have evolved over time in an interplay with social institutions and, second, the presupposition that there is inevitably a plurality of such orders: 'more than one and less than many' (Mol and Law 2020).

Boltanski and Thévenot (2006) identified six 'orders of justification' that have historically developed into a widely shared moral repertoire for modern societies, each defining a specific understanding of 'worth': the civic world centres on political belonging, the industrial on efficiency, the market on success, the domestic on tradition, the inspired on creativity, and the world of fame on public opinion. These orders have evolved historically as part of the emergence of societal institutions and organisational forms, such as the nation-state and its conception of citizenship, the market, the factory, or the family. Orders of justification are accordingly anchored in social relations and practices that can be experienced on an everyday basis. Social actors can therefore be expected to not only be familiar, but to have incorporated these varying moral and political logics.

Derouet (1992, 2000, 2019) applied the framework of plural moral orders to the educational field. He identified five 'school worlds' that inform how we nowadays conceive of school education. These are: a civic school world concentrating on the role of school education for modern citizenship, an industrial school world focused on standardized and efficient learning of skills needed in labour markets, a market school world centred on notions of success, an inspired school world emphasising creativity and self-fulfilment, and a domestic school world which underlines traditional values and hierarchies. Similar to orders of justification, these school worlds are not purely discursive phenomena. Rather, each of them relates various aspects of school education in its own specific ways, from what is seen as an ideal teacher-student relation to preferred forms of instruction and typical learning environments or classroom architecture (Holmqvist and Telling 2024; Imdorf and Leemann 2023).

Importantly for this article, each of these school worlds comes with its own conception of educational justice (Holmqvist 2022; Horvath and Steinberg 2023). What counts as 'good' and 'fair' varies depending on how the purposes of school education are defined and what relations between education and the common good are emphasised.

How does this tenet of plural moral orders advance our understanding of problematisation dynamics, specifically of justice issues in the context of EdTech and AIED? First and foremost, the notion of school worlds makes the persistence and broad acceptability of AIED narratives understandable. Being firmly anchored in well-established school-worlds, the problematisations surrounding AIED are actually very much oriented towards the past and the present – belying their claims of rupture and innovation and their rhetorical references to imagined futures. Elements of an industrial school world play a role in dominant AIED problematisations, where AI is presented as a means to increase the efficiency of school education. But overall, the moral grammar underlying public AIED narratives resonates primarily with an inspired school-world understanding, including dominant notions of educational justice. Good and fair school education is imagined to be all about creativity and self-fulfilment. An early and influential example for this problematisation is Ken Robinson's famous TED-Talk that to this day has been viewed almost 80 million times.² The problem with current schooling is seen in an over-emphasis on knowledge acquisition and its one-size-fits-all character. Contestation of standardized curricula, of lacking space for creativity, of disciplinary regimes reminiscent of factories, and of teaching to the test are routine elements of these problematisations. In AIED-related narratives, these features of school education (associated with civic and industrial school worlds) are denounced as inappropriate for our times because they supposedly ignore both the affordances of novel technologies and the requirements of a digitised post-industrial economy and society. At this point, school world logics are interlocked with broader economic and political framings, reminiscent of the 'new spirit of capitalism' that defines a novel, invigorated ethos of entrepreneurship (Boltansk and Chiapello, 2018).

Beyond sensitizing us to this foundation in established understandings of school education, the tenet of plural moral orders suggests three important lines of analysis:

- (1) *Unravelling silent assumptions*: Problematisations that are firmly anchored in established moral grammars can afford to be elliptic – they seem self-evident and therefore are under no pressure to make underlying assumptions explicit. The tenet of plural moral orders invites us to explicate these silent assumptions. For dominant AIED narratives, we might, for example, scrutinize and problematise the links that are silently established between *personalisation* and *justice*. This interlocking is a key feature of their solutionist rhetoric: AIED is believed to increase educational justice through radically personalizing learning according to the interests, needs, strengths, and talents of each and every individual child (Horvath, Frei, and Steinberg 2023; Dishon 2017).

The link between personalisation and justice is thus established using an inspired school world logic. At closer sight, this presupposed interlocking is not at all self-evident or tautologically true. Other school worlds suggest other conceptions of educational justice. Justice could, for example, be tied to the equalizing (not personalising) role of school education or to the emancipatory power of shared (not personalised) learning experiences. Starting from a civic or an industrial school-world, one would hence problematise issues of educational justice otherwise. Pointing to these alternative logics is a first step towards a more nuanced critical engagement with AIED and its role for educational justice.

- (2) *Explicating tensions*: Even more importantly, the link between personalisation and justice through an inspired school-world logic is far more precarious and questionable than presented. Upon closer examination, there are strong historical links between ideas of personalised learning and the ideals of an industrial school-world. Skinner's strongly behaviourist 'learning machine' exemplifies this tension (Skinner 1958; du Boulay 2019): while this machine was designed to personalise learning pathways, it did so to increase efficiency rather than creativity; it focused on standardised skills rather than on self-expression or creativity; and it relied on measurement frameworks that follow an industrial rather than an inspired school-world logic.

This historical example reveals how personalisation can be aligned with industrial rather than inspired values, despite contemporary rhetoric suggesting otherwise. Social actors will often not be aware of such tensions but rather navigate between them as if no ruptures existed. Thus, it is not uncommon that teachers, when talking about everyday classroom situations, shift without notice between civic, market, industrial, inspired, and domestic logics of educational quality and justice. Making such tensions explicit as they arise in AIED contexts opens them up for debate.

- (3) *Identifying ruptures*: Taking the step from discursive framing to real-world arrangements of teaching and learning, the tenet of plural moral orders suggests looking for ruptures that occur between the discourses framing a phenomenon as a problem and the practices and processes set in place to actually deal with this problem. Turning to the AIED example, in our research we frequently observed that the data used by and the algorithms coded into EdTech tools did not match their discursive framing (Horvath, Frei, and Steinberg 2023, 2024).

For example, tools that are presented as adapting to individual 'interests' or 'talents' commonly employ psychometric achievement scales to personalise learning pathways. In other words: they operate on skills measures, not on indicators for 'interests', 'needs', or 'talents'. The identification of such ruptures requires that we move from the discursive realm of problematisation to the situational agency of designing and deploying such tools.

These three analytical moves – unravelling assumptions, explicating tensions, and identifying ruptures – are an important foundation for exploring how problematisations 'materialise' in practice. They shift attention to the level of moral grammars that link public narratives to situational practices (even if in discontinuous ways). While the observations presented in this section are selective and sketchy, they suggest patterns that may have broader relevance for understanding the transformation of justice concerns in educational technology.

The plurality of widely shared understandings of school education also helps understand how EdTech narratives can maintain their aura of self-evidence and thus persist despite obvious tensions and contradictions. However, to fully understand how these narratives affect the development of AIED, we need to examine how they relate to concrete problem-solving activities of designing and deploying these tools.

The next section therefore turns to the development contexts around Swiss EdTech startups. Using selected examples from our ongoing research, we examine how problematic dynamics of 'short-circuiting' emerge when connections presented as self-evident in public narratives neglect crucial considerations in the actual development of AIED technologies.

We use the term short-circuiting to describe situations where complex relationships are simplified in ways that allow certain problems or considerations to be bypassed without explicit acknowledgment – similar to how an electrical short-circuit bypasses part of a circuit's intended path. Such dynamics are troubling because they come with intricate dynamics of reframing and thereby partly invisibilising justice concerns.

EdTech in the making: from problematisations to problem-solving agency

While plural moral orders have become the most recognised aspect of French Pragmatic Sociology (Boltanski and Thévenot 2006), the quintessential point of FPS is how actors draw on these orders *to coordinate in uncertain situations*. This situational focus requires us to distinguish between problematisations as widely shared discursive resources and the concrete problem-solving activities of social actors in their everyday professional contexts. Examining this relationship is crucial for understanding how problematisations 'materialise.' The following analysis of EdTech startup practices demonstrates the analytical power of this approach by revealing how public narratives and everyday problem-solving interact in ways that transform justice concerns.

Our focus in the following is on the EdTech startup scene. This is of course only part of the AIED landscape, with large corporations and their platform economics playing a major role in the development of novel technologies (Williamson 2018, 2022). While large tech corporations shape the digital infrastructure within which startups operate, their largely black-boxed practices and internal dynamics are beyond the scope of this article's analysis. Our focus on startups has proven to deliver crucial insights into how AIED solutions materialise in practice, even though their accessibility required considerable groundwork. Our analysis of the startup field should, in any case, be understood as exploring what our theoretical framework can reveal about problematisation-materialisation processes, rather than as comprehensive claims about all EdTech development contexts.

Importantly, the emblem of EdTech startups is itself part of the dominant AIED narrative, as became evident in our pilot study on current EdTech discourse. The startup notion is deeply anchored in these discourses through the very politico-economic moral grammar of entrepreneurship (Boltanski and Chiapello 2018) mentioned in the previous section. The strong references to 'disruption' and 'innovation' in public AIED narratives build on the Silicon Valley credo of the founder's genius and creativity, leading to a widely accepted assumption that the organisational form of startups is required to bring about necessary innovation, following the example of the tech-industry. On this basis, a seeming coherence between the visions for school education and overarching entrepreneurial myths form, strengthened by arguments about the skills needed for succeeding in the labour markets of the future: out-of-the-box thinking, creative problem solving, and team-working.

The imagination of EdTech startups as privileged social form for disruptive educational change has material and institutional consequences. It provides the rationale for building a whole EdTech startup 'eco-system,' often heavily funded by public institutions. For example, the European Schoolnet (ESN), a network of European education ministries, hosts its own 'startup incubator-accelerator' named 'EdTech Impact,' with the aim 'to boost innovation in education, helping European digital education innovators to bring their digital learning solutions into the market' (Schoolnet 2020).

What problem-solving activities can we expect in such EdTech startup settings, how are they related to dominant problematisations – and what consequences may that have, for example for how matters of social justice are handled in AIED? Following the tenet of plural school worlds, the thorough consideration of such justice issues would have to face two tasks: first, the clarification of the understanding of educational justice at play, second the careful reflection of how tools and technologies built on this basis should or could be integrated into already complex concrete school-world arrangements.

Perhaps unsurprisingly, our research shows that startup developers deal with situational problems that are very different from these concerns: their agency concentrates on the more immediate existential challenges that EdTech entrepreneurs face. The route to success for startups is in the first place a struggle to survive. Not only are working and living conditions often precarious, the financing of business is clearly the crucial activity on which everything else hinges. Financing can be secured in different ways – through business angels, public funding, or private resources – but in any case it is the main problem that needs to be dealt with on a daily basis.

The overriding relevance of securing investment and financial survival in combination with the spirit of entrepreneurship is a pervasive feature of the field as we encountered it in our research. It is expressed in different events that startups take part in, from hackathons to fairs and EdTech summits. At such events, startups either face different kinds of ‘tests’, for instance pitching contests, or they prepare for succeeding in them by attending on-site workshops, motivational keynote talks, or networking sessions. These ‘tests’ all revolve around convincing investors rather than demonstrating educational or social impact.

The focus on securing investment makes a key task for startups all the more demanding: an active engagement with actors from the school-field. In our interviews, EdTech startups regularly report their lack of contact with teachers and other pedagogical actors as one of their main challenges. While startups of course require a clear idea of the needs and preferences of their future customers (schools, students, teachers, parents etc.), their products in the first place have to convince investors, not practitioners. This implies that the voices and concerns of educational actors are often only very indirectly considered when EdTech startups define and handle the situations in which they develop their products.

What does this constellation imply for the handling of justice concerns? Considering the side-lining of educational actors, one might expect a widespread neglect of justice concerns. The actual picture is more nuanced. Some startups in our sample do develop products with explicit equity aims, and many individuals express personal commitment to justice concerns (cf. Macgilchrist 2019). The key point is that justice issues are framed according to a different moral repertoire – they are staged and addressed as a business problem, as expressed in the following quote: ‘Social impact, a second factor, we look at it as having an SDG as the main, the main company focus [...] the core product of the business.’

This represents a fundamental shift away from the moral grammar of school worlds that would require, first, clarifying which conception of justice is at stake (civic equality? industrial efficiency? inspired self-fulfilment?). Second, it would also imply careful consideration of how technologies affect complex classroom arrangements in which more often than not several different understandings of educational justice interact in complex ways. Instead, justice issues are disconnected from these educational concerns and rephrased as a question of scaling. Notions such as the United Nations’ Sustainable Development Goals (SDG)

present a fitting framing because they allow startups to emphasize a concern for equity issues (on a global scale!) while remaining anchored in logics of business and development. This scaling logic is regularly generalised and used independent of SDGs or similar notions. As one of our interview partners put it: ‘It must be suitable for the masses. With us, all children in [city] could in fact benefit, it would be a help for all children.’ Scaling becomes the full answer to the problem of educational injustice – from a school-world perspective a troubling oversimplification that bypasses both the pluralistic understandings of justice and the complex realities of educational practice.

The structural pressures of securing investment mean that even well-intentioned equity initiatives must ultimately be justified through their market potential. This configuration has further important and sometimes counter-intuitive consequences. For example, the struggle for investment actually – and ironically – limits the scope for rupture and innovation supposedly at the heart of startup entrepreneurship. For startups, it often is wiser to play it safe rather than to be as disruptive as public narratives celebrate. Employing novel digital technologies is risky. Accordingly, the employment of commercial Large Language Models, for example, is highly strategic and instrumental. Once there is a hype that affects the expectations of financiers (and, even if only in the second line, customers), it makes sense to look for a place to integrate that technological aspect or device in one’s tool. As one startup explained: ‘I think if you have the feeling or claim that we don’t need AI, even if you could justify it, but for that you would have to have already dealt with the topic very well, then it is immediately said that you’re not open to new things.’

For the context of this article, this tendency towards well-balanced and risk-averse (rather than disruptive) innovation is important because it leads to design choices that run counter to the discursive framings of the kind of solution that AIED delivers – and to what kind of problem. While the dominant narratives surrounding EdTech strongly link personalisation and justice through references to an ‘inspired’ school-world, many AIED devices actually employ algorithms that build on psychometric scales as they are known from large-scale assessment studies and standardised achievement tests. These scales are of course also deeply interwoven with conceptions of educational justice and equity, but on the basis of a very different moral grammar. They are expressive of ‘industrial’ and partly also of ‘civic’ school worlds, in which school education is all about conveying shared curricular knowledge and skills in efficient and standardised ways. The choice of such psychometric scales makes sense from an EdTech startup’s point of view. These scales are well established and unquestionably acceptable to investors and prospective customers. The problem arises as soon as the affordances of these devices are misrepresented regarding the very understanding of educational justice they express and how this form of educational justice can be achieved.

Returning to the materialisation of problematisations, a nuanced picture results from our exploratory observations. There is a pronounced discontinuity between school-world elements staged in public narratives and actual product development:

- Public narratives structure EdTech development not primarily through direct application of educational principles, but through their politico-economic foundation. The ethos of entrepreneurship, rather than educational quality and justice concerns, appears to tie public discourse and product development together in the contexts we observed.

- Public education-centred problematisations are still effective in situations of AIED development. The existence of these broadly accepted narratives is a resource for startups because they constitute a widely shared repertoire of assumptions and presuppositions on the interrelations between the problems of modern school education, the digital era, and AI-based technologies. They therefore are helpful for startups because they allow to retain compatibility with and accessibility to the educational world while focusing on realising their business plan. These narratives also allow involved actors to neglect the question of alignment between tool design, conceptions of educational justice and quality, and envisioned learning environments – these issues can be silently treated as being ‘already solved.’

The misalignment between expected and actual problem-solving practices, along with the situational constellations of actors and issues in which startups operate, helps explain how social justice concerns become reframed and partly invisibilised despite their salience in public discourse about AIED. They are visible as a different kind of problem (a problem of scale), while aspects important for understanding effects and implications of digital tools in real-world contexts are not systematically taken into account.

From the standpoint of pragmatic sociology, this analysis leads back to the role of critical sociology: How should sociologists engage with these dynamics given that they are neither neutral observers nor external critics, but themselves part of the educational field? What role can and should critical sociology play in making justice concerns more central to the actual tests that AIED faces? The following section addresses these questions by examining the epistemological tenet of complex interiority and its implications for critical engagement with AIED development.

Sociology’s role: from analysis to enabling critical engagement

The starting point for our discussion of FPS was the question of how exactly we can think of AIED as ‘materialised problematisations.’ For the case of AIED, we argue that the interplay between public narratives and situational agency leads to troubling dynamics of (in-)visibilising social justice concerns. This friction between grand narratives and everyday problem-solving activities raises crucial questions about how problematisations themselves might be reproblematised. How can sociologists engage with these dynamics while acknowledging their own position within educational fields? What concrete tasks might enable more meaningful integration of justice concerns into AIED development?

Different strands of French Pragmatic Sociology answer these questions differently (Boltanski 2011; Couldry 2020; Latour 2004, 2009). We focus on Boltanski’s Sociology of Critique which offers an answer that revolves around three aspects:

- (1) *Acknowledging sociology’s complex interiority*: Following Boltanski’s (2011) epistemological principle of ‘complex interiority,’ we must recognise that sociologists occupy no privileged epistemic position outside the moral orders they analyse. Since pragmatic sociology recognises a plurality of widely accepted understandings of social justice, we cannot provide a single definition of what social justice means, but rather need to explore how different conceptions are mobilized and negotiated in concrete contexts such as the development of AIED. As researchers, we are inevitably embedded within these established notions of social justice (Barthe et al. 2014).

For pragmatic sociologists, this is not an invitation to relativism, but rather a precondition for meaningful involvement (Putnam 2002). Only by acknowledging our embeddedness within plural moral grammars can we engage with dominant problematisations. We can point to tensions within them and outline the silent assumptions they build on. The decisive point is to be transparent about how one's position as a researcher and one's analysis are informed by the network of justice notions we encounter (Baert 2005). In AIED contexts, this might mean taking sides, for example by arguing for a true and more radical implementation of inspired school world principles that avoids silently 'falling back' into industrial logics of increasing efficiency and standardised testing. It could also mean explicitly anchoring one's intervention in a civic understanding of educational justice and on this basis to critically question the desirability of inspired school world imaginations. Being transparent about how one navigates school worlds becomes the key demand.

On an analytical level, acknowledging this plurality allows us to understand how plural orders enable both stabilisation (through subtle compromises between different notions of educational quality and justice) and transformation (through making visible alternative problematisations that yield pressure for change).

- (2) *Explicating short-circuits*: Our key analytical task then involves identifying what we choose to call 'short-circuits' – connections presented as self-evident that actually conceal complex and often questionable assumptions. In dominant AIED discourses, the equation of personalisation with justice represents one such short-circuit, suggesting that any technology that personalises learning automatically advances educational equity. This dangerous elision, among others, neglects the well-documented risks of algorithmic bias inherent in personalisation technologies (Baker and Hawn 2022; Eynon 2024; Gillani et al. 2023).

Similarly, our research reveals a further short-circuit when 'adaptivity to student interests and talents' gets operationalised through psychometric achievement scales – a translation that relies on questionable assumptions about the relationship between test performance and individual interests, talents, and needs. The strong association assumed between disruption, innovation, and startups as organisational form provides another example for a powerful and consequential short-circuit. Finally, we might explicate the assumptions that are silenced when educational fairness is conceived of in business terms as a problem of scale.

It is a key tenet of the Sociology of Critique that social actors have the capacity to recognise and understand such problematic tensions and ruptures when confronted with them, but lack opportunities to reflect on them amid everyday pressures. By explicating these short-circuits, we can help break open technological fixes (solutions that seemed unproblematic and without alternative) and broaden the range of options that actors perceive and can deliberately choose among. Critical sociology can thus contribute to widening and deepening spaces for deliberation about alternative approaches to educational justice in AIED:

- (3) *Re-embedding justice in material practices*: Perhaps most importantly, pragmatic sociology suggests considering how we can make social justice matter by re-thinking the kind of 'tests' that AIED products have to go through during their development

and deployment. Thus, our analysis points to an urgent need for thinking about ways to include more and other voices and concerns in situations that AIED developers face. Current startup ecosystems provide no systematic mechanisms for evaluating justice implications that aligns with actual school worlds, in many cases relegating equity to optional marketing rhetoric rather than necessary development criteria.

Addressing this structural gap would require new types of ‘tests’ for startups, at the expense of those that currently dominate their entrepreneurial journey. This might take the form of formal and explicit testing, such as certification requirements that verify empirical evidence of equity effects. It might also take the form of testing actual effects through monitoring systems that track differential impacts across demographic groups. Or we may think of more implicit, but also perhaps more profound and more flexible forms of testing by bringing developers, teachers, parents, students, and researchers together in ‘deliberative forums’ (Swist and Gulson, 2023; Horvath, Steinberg, and Frei 2023a). While sociological research alone cannot create these spaces, it can model such deliberative practices through participatory research methods and advocate for institutional changes that embed these forums in EdTech development processes. While these interventions may seem ambitious, they represent concrete steps toward ensuring that social justice concerns become materially embedded in AIED development rather than remaining rhetorical flourishes in public discourse.

Conclusion

This article has introduced the Sociology of Critique as a framework for understanding how problematisations ‘materialise’ in AIED and how this affects social justice considerations. Our dual contribution lies in both refining the concept of problematisation through French Pragmatic Sociology and demonstrating its analytical utility through an examination of justice dynamics in the current EdTech field.

By tracing the relationship between public narratives and problem-solving activities, we’ve presented three key analytical tools: the analysis of plural moral grammars that inform understandings of educational quality and justice; the identification of tensions and ruptures that arise in and between school worlds; and the concept of ‘short-circuiting,’ where connections presented as self-evident allow complex considerations to be bypassed without explicit acknowledgment – a key mechanism through which problematisations are transformed as they materialise in practice. Through these tools, we have illuminated how AIED narratives mobilise inspired school-world rhetoric, while actual development practices remain governed by entrepreneurial imperatives and ‘industrial’ testing frameworks.

Our exploratory observations of startup practices demonstrate how this framework can reveal dynamics that might otherwise remain invisible by shifting attention to how EdTech entrepreneurs navigate between grand problematisations and immediate survival challenges in ways that transform how justice concerns are addressed. Rather than being ignored, justice issues are reframed through business logics that equate scale with equity, creating a pronounced gap between rhetoric and implementation. The resulting short-circuits conceal complex questions about what educational justice means and how technologies affect classroom arrangements.

It is important to acknowledge the scope of our investigation into how problematisations ‘materialise.’ This article examines the situations and contexts in which design happens rather than analysing actual designs or design processes in detail. While we have taken important steps toward understanding the transformation of problematisations as they move from discourse to practice, a complete account of materialisation would require additional research into the technical specifics of AIED designs, algorithmic decision-making processes, and classroom implementation. Our contribution lies in illuminating the social dynamics that shape how justice concerns are transformed in development contexts, offering a foundation for future research that might examine the full materialisation journey across technical and pedagogical dimensions.

Future research could productively build on this framework by examining how problematisations materialise across different educational technology contexts, comparing startup and corporate development environments, or investigating how teachers and students engage with these technologies in practice. Longitudinal studies tracing the full journey of problematisations from public discourse to classroom implementation would be particularly valuable for understanding the complete materialisation process.

These insights have implications for several domains beyond academic research. For EdTech governance, they suggest the need for regulatory approaches that can identify and interrupt problematic ‘short-circuiting’ rather than relying solely on market mechanisms or post-hoc evaluation. For research-practice partnerships, they suggest the need for new forms of collaboration and arenas for critical dialogue that embed justice considerations in development processes rather than treating them as add-on concerns. For teacher education, they highlight the importance of developing educators’ critical literacy about the moral grammars embedded in educational technologies and their capacity to participate actively in technology evaluation and design.

Taken together, these various implications point to a productive role for sociology that moves beyond critique-as-denunciation toward critique-as-engagement. Sociology’s task lies in helping to make justice concerns matter by reproblematising the problematisations that shape educational technology. By explicating short-circuits and fostering deliberative spaces where diverse voices can engage with these dynamics, critical sociology can help transform not just how we understand AIED, but how it is designed, developed, and deployed in relation to the complex moral orders that shape educational worlds.

Notes

1. When we talk of AIED in this article, we refer to algorithmic devices that employ Machine Learning, Large-Language-Models or similar techniques to identify patterns in large amount of data. Such algorithms can be employed for different purposes in education, such as adaptive learning and ‘intelligent’ tutoring systems, essay helpers that provide formative feedback on writing tasks, predictions of students’ success or failure, or interactive teacher dashboards.
2. https://www.ted.com/talks/sir_ken_robinson_do_schools_kill_creativity [accessed 15/02/2025]

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How do problematisations “materialise”? A neopragmatic perspective on the (in-)visibilisation of justice concerns in AIED

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